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Research Article

**CO-ENZYME Q-10: PREVENTIVE EFFECTS IN INH
INDUCED HEPATOTOXICITY IN ALBINO WISTAR RATS****Shahnaz Bano Menon¹, Abdul Rahim Memon², Ashique Ali Arain³,
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Department of Pharmacology, Isra University Hyderabad.⁴MBBS, M.Phil(Pharmacology), Assistant Professor, Isra University, Hyderabad.⁵MBBS, M.Phil (Pharmacology), Assistant Professor, Isra University, Hyderabad.**Abstract:**

Tuberculosis is a common disease of the sub-continent and most of the anti-tuberculosis drugs are hepatotoxic, INH (Isoniazid) being on the top in this regard. We tried to explore the hepatoprotective aspects of the Q-10(Co-enzyme) in the current study in rat model by artificially inducing the hepatotoxicity by INH. Albino Westar rats were purchased from Karachi (n=50) then divided into 5 equal groups (A,B,C,D,E) and left for acclimatization for two weeks periods. Group A was kept intervention free as control while group B was induced with INH 100 mg/day orally (n=10) as negative control and others groups C was given INH 100mg+CoQ 100mg/day orally (n=10), group D. INH 150+ CoQ 100mg/day orally (n=10) and E. INH 200mg+CoQ 100mg/day orally (n=10). Blood samples were drawn after 1 month interventional period and liver function test were performed and comparison was done between the mean values using ANOVA on SPSS version 22. It was observed that there was statistically highly significant difference in serum concentrations of AST(0.00001), ALT(0.0007), LDH(0.000010), ALP(0.00001), GGT(0.0004) among the experimental group.

Conclusion: Co-enzyme Q-10 possesses hepatoprotective properties against the INH induced hepatotoxicity in a concentration dependent manner.

Key Words: ALT, AST, LDH, GGT.

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QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Coenzyme Q10 is found in whole body especially in the kidney, liver, cardiac and brain tissue [1, 2]. This vitamin resembling compound is soluble in fat and a part of cellular mitochondrial respiratory chain along with its antioxidant properties [3]. It is also known as Ubiquinol, ubiquinone, and used as food and therapeutic agent in various countries in USA it is the 3rd common most supplement to be consumed after multivitamins and omega-3 fatty acids [3, 4]. Biosynthesis of CoQ10 occurs in the same process as the cholesterol by HMG Co-A reductase from the acetyl-CoA molecules so the use of statins results into 40% reduction in its serum levels. [5,6]. Co-Q10 gets absorbed from the small intestine like other fat soluble substances through bile salts and micelle formation reaching to maximum levels in 2-6 hours. [7,8]. It is well distributed substance but its metabolism is yet to be discovered with half-life of 33 hours it is excreted through feces [9]. Studies have proven that Co-Q10 is effective in multiple diseases like Parkinsonism, diabetes mellitus (DM), cardiac diseases, muscle dystrophy and cancer along with other conditions due to its associated low concentration in these illnesses [10-13]. INH (Isoniazid) is among the main drugs available for eradication of tuberculosis round the globe but its use is associated with mild to moderate hepatitis at the initiation of therapy which accounts for about 10% disturbing the liver functions accordingly [14-16]. This hepatic toxicity is due to its toxic metabolite resulting into idiosyncrasy in certain individuals [17,18]. INH is effective against the mycobacterium tuberculosis but mycobacterium Kansasi also responds to it at higher doses and other NTM are resistant to it. INH is a prodrug that needs activation by the mycobacteria itself. It is well distributed agent in all body compartments (cells, CSF and caseous material). The drug is metabolized through hydrolysis and acetylation and excreted in urine and the half-life ranges from 90 minutes to 4 hours for fast and slow acetylators respectively [19,20]. The current research was managed to explore the beneficial effects of Co-Q10 so that it may be recommended for use along with INH and other Anti tuberculosis drugs to avoid the undesired effects on liver to improve the compliance and the prognosis.

METHODOLOGY:

Study was approved by the ERC and BASR Isra University Hyderabad Pakistan and animals were purchased through inclusion/exclusion criteria. Rats were acclimatized for 2 wks at Animal house of Sindh Agricultural University of Tando Jam after being divided into 5 groups. Hepatic toxicity was induced by using higher dose of INH. Group A was administered normal saline and no intervention was given (control group), group B was given INH 100 mg/day orally (n=10) (Induced group) group C was treated with INH 100mg and Co-Q10 100mg/day, group D was given INH 150+ Co-Q10 100mg/day while group E was given INH 200mg+Co-Q10 100mg/day. Oral route was adopted for drug administration, samples of blood from all rats were obtained after cervical dislocation after 1 month. Liver function test (LFTs) were performed in the Isra Research lab. Mean value of the serum ALP, ALT, AST and gamma GT were compared using ANOVA on SPSS version 22.

RESULTS:

There was a highly significant difference in ALT levels (Group A 24.2±8.6), (group B 39.4±8.3), (group C 30.2±7.8), (group D 32.4±6.1) and (group E 33.1±9.4) with p-value 0.0007 and AST levels were found as (group A 29.6±10.9), (group B 89.6±12.0), (group C 77.4±16.8), (group D 80.5±13.2) and (group E 82.4±9.6) among the experimental groups p=0.00001 (Table 01). Serum LDH levels were found as (group A 59.5±17.9), (group B 122.2±9.7), (group C 101.5±14.7), (group D 109.7±14.2) and (group E 111.0±15.3) highly significant p-value 0.00001 in study rats while serum ALP levels were noted as (group A 50.2±8.2), (group B 114.3±18.6), (group C 94.9±18.2), (group D 99.0±18.6) and (group E 101.9±19.2) p-value 0.00001 which was highly significant (Table 02). Serum GGT levels were observed as (group A 16.6±3.2), (group B 58.4±12.2), (group C 49.2±6.0), (group D 53.6±6.5) and (group E 55.1±6.3) p-value was 0.00001 which is highly significant. Serum bilirubin measured was (group A 0.46±0.18), (group B 2.0±0.61), (group C 1.73±0.430), (group D 1.97±0.43) and (group E 2.06±0.52) with highly significant p-value 0.00004 (Table 03).

Table 01. Comparison of serum ALT and AST among the study groups (n=50)

Parameters	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	F-Ratio	P-value
ALT (IU/L)	24.2±8.6	39.4±8.3	30.2±7.8	32.4±6.1	33.1±9.4	5.84	0.0007
AST (IU/L)	29.6±10.9	89.6±12.0	77.4±16.8	80.5±13.2	82.4±9.6	35.69	0.00001

Table 02. Comparison of serum LDH and ALP among the study groups(n=50)

Parameters	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	F-Ratio	P-value
LDH (IU/L)	59.5±17.9	122.2±9.7	101.5±14.7	109.7±14.2	111.0±15.3	27.52	0.00001
ALP (U/L)	50.2±8.2	114.3±18.6	94.9±18.2	99.0±18.6	101.9±19.2	20.56	0.00001

Table 03. Comparison of serum γ -GT and Bilirubin among the study groups(n=50)

Parameters	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	F-Ratio	P-value
γ -GT (IU/L)	16.6±3.2	58.4±12.2	49.2±6.0	53.6±6.5	55.1±6.3	54.08	0.00001
Bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.46±0.18	2.0±0.61	1.73±0.43	1.97±0.43	2.06±0.52	21.72	0.00004

DISCUSSION:

We could not find any study in the literature regarding evaluation of Co-Q10 against the INH induced hepatotoxicity so this totally a new add in this field research but its protective effects against some other agents have been reported by some authors. Eghbal, et al reported a consistent finding to our results that was protective role of Q10 against the statin induced hepatic injury his study was in vitro on the isolated hepatocytes from the rat liver. However the study parameters were different from our work his research was based on glutathione levels, membrane lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial membrane potential, free radical formation and hepatocyte death, oxygen derived free radical formation (21) These findings strongly support our results regarding hepatoprotective role of Co-Q 10. Another consistent study with our findings was by Farsi et al (2015) showing the hepatoprotective effect of Co-Q10 administration against the non-alcoholic liver disease which is consistent to our study. Although his parameters studied were same as our but he also evaluated some other markers like adipokines, and inflammatory markers [22]. This study has reported the improvement in serum AST, ALT, GGT, TNF- α and CRP levels by the Co-Q10. We could not evaluate the other parameters covered by Farsi et al due to our financial as well as technical reasons as it was not in our primary objectives this is weakness of our study but at the same time it became a way and a gap for others to carry on.

Few other studies available on literature search demonstrate the protective effects of the Co-Q10 against the drug induced tissue injuries of various organs like nephropathy[23], neuropathy[24], Reproductive organs[25] but these studies not on liver so we cannot compare them with our finding but these studies mentioned the anti-oxidative role of the Co-Q10 behind its tissue protective effect. We hope this research work will

give a base to interested researchers to explore further possible mechanisms of the agent under discussion.

CONCLUSION:

Co-Q10 effectively prevented the hepatotoxicity in the experimental animals in a dose dependent manner.

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